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TRANSFORMATION OF TAX MECHANISMS FOR STIMULATING INVESTMENT ACTIVITY IN THE CONTEXT OF SANCTIONS RESTRICTIONS

The article considers the evolution of tax mechanisms for stimulating investment activity in the Russian Federation in the context of external restrictions. The author analyzes the transformation of the regulatory framework and instruments of tax incentives for investment. The study reveals the features of the application of various tax instruments in the context of sanctions pressure, including investment tax deduction, special tax regimes for territories with special economic status, tax benefits for participants in special investment contracts. Particular attention is paid to assessing the effectiveness of the applied tax mechanisms from the standpoint of their impact on investment activity and sectoral transformation of the economy. For a comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of tax mechanisms for stimulating investment activity, a multifactor approach was used in the work, including an analysis of the dynamics of investment in fixed assets in comparison with the volume of tax expenditures (lost revenues of the budget system due to the use of tax incentives), as well as an assessment of the impact of tax incentives on structural changes in the economy. Particular attention should be paid to the analysis of the impact of tax mechanisms on

attracting investment in high-tech industries, which are a key factor in ensuring technological sovereignty in the context of sanctions. The study shows that the greatest effect in stimulating investment in high-tech production is achieved with the comprehensive use of various tax mechanisms, including income tax benefits, investment tax deductions and accelerated depreciation. An important factor is the stability of tax legislation and the predictability of tax policy, which is especially important for long-term investment projects. Based on the study, recommendations were formed to improve tax mechanisms for stimulating investment activity in the context of ensuring the financial and technological sovereignty of the Russian Federation.

Keywords: tax incentives, investment activity, tax breaks, investment tax deduction.

2022 , 2014

(2014-2019 .)

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31.12.2014 488- «
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0% , ,

29.12.2014 473- «
»

(0% 5%
10%),
(7,6 % 30 %
)[3].

27.11.2017 335- .286.1 ,

COVID-19, (2020-2021 .)

2020 31.07.2020 258- «
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31.07.2020 269- 2.0.

2.0 ,
(2)

265- 31.07.2020
 3%, — 7,6%
 (2022 .)
 2022
 26.03.2022 67-
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 09.03.2022 (),
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 14.07.2022 323-
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 [2].
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 2014-2021 .
 22,9 .. 64,7% 13,9 .
 5,2%, (-)
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 2,3 , 1,2 . 2,8 ..
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(,)	93,7	1245,8	13,3	,
	27,1	312,4	11,5	-
-	63,4	518,2	8,2	,
-	16,8	357,6	21,3	,

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(13,3), (,)

11,5), (

(8,2), - ,

2014-2022 .
 15,1% 17,8%, — 2,8% 5,3%. — 3,7% 4,2%, -
 18,9% 15,2%,

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(0,68),

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